

Supplementary Information

PlanktonFlow : hands-on deep-learning classification of plankton images for biologists

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S1 Supplementary Methods

S1.1 Loss function algorithms

Algorithm 1 Computation of Focal Loss (per sample)

Require: Logits $\mathbf{o} \in \mathbb{R}^C$, ground-truth label $y \in \{1, \dots, C\}$, focusing parameter γ , optional weight vector $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$

Ensure: Focal loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{focal}}$

- 1: **function** FOCALLOSS($\mathbf{o}, y, \gamma, \boldsymbol{\alpha}$)
 - 2: Compute softmax probabilities: $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \leftarrow \text{softmax}(\mathbf{o})$
 - 3: Extract true class probability: $p_t \leftarrow \hat{y}_y$
 - 4: Clamp p_t to avoid $\log(0)$ (e.g., $p_t \leftarrow \text{clamp}(p_t, \varepsilon, 1 - \varepsilon)$)
 - 5: Compute modulating factor: $m \leftarrow (1 - p_t)^\gamma$
 - 6: **if** $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is defined **then** $a_t \leftarrow \alpha_y$ **else** $a_t \leftarrow 1$
 - 7: Compute focal loss: $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow -a_t \cdot m \cdot \log(p_t)$
 - 8: **return** \mathcal{L}
 - 9: **end function**
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Algorithm 2 Computation of Label Smoothing Loss (redistributing smoothing over incorrect classes)

Require: Logits \mathbf{o} , ground-truth labels \mathbf{y} , smoothing factor ϵ , number of classes C

Ensure: Label smoothing loss \mathcal{L}_{LS}

- 1: **function** LABELSMOOTHINGLOSS($\mathbf{o}, \mathbf{y}, \epsilon$)
- 2: Construct one-hot labels: $\mathbf{y}_{\text{one-hot}}$
- 3: Apply label smoothing:

$$\tilde{y}_c = \begin{cases} 1 - \epsilon & \text{if } c = y \\ \frac{\epsilon}{C-1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

- 4: Compute log-probabilities: $\log \hat{\mathbf{y}} \leftarrow \log \text{softmax}(\mathbf{o})$
 - 5: Compute loss: $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow -\sum_{c=1}^C \tilde{y}_c \cdot \log \hat{y}_c$
 - 6: **return** \mathcal{L}
 - 7: **end function**
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S1.2 Learning Rate Scheduling

In addition to optimizer selection, the learning rate was dynamically adjusted throughout training using a cosine annealing schedule. Specifically, we used PyTorch’s `CosineAnnealingLR`, which gradually decreases the learning rate following a cosine function over a fixed number of epochs. This approach encourages larger updates at the beginning of training and finer adjustments toward the end, helping the model settle into better minima.

At each epoch t , the learning rate η_t is computed as:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{\min} + \frac{1}{2}(\eta_0 - \eta_{\min}) \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{t\pi}{T_{\max}} \right) \right) \quad (\text{S1})$$

where η_0 is the initial learning rate, η_{\min} is the minimum learning rate (often set to 0), t is the current epoch, and T_{\max} is the total number of epochs before a full cosine cycle completes.

S1.3 Early Stopping Strategy

To prevent unnecessary training time, an **early stopping** mechanism was implemented (see Algorithm 3). This method monitors the validation loss and, optionally, the validation accuracy, halting training when no improvement is observed for a specified number of consecutive epochs (referred to as the *patience* parameter).

Our implementation allows for two simultaneous criteria:

- Validation loss must improve by at least a threshold δ (default: 0).
- If enabled, validation accuracy must also improve by at least δ .

Formally, let \mathcal{L}_t and \mathcal{A}_t denote the validation loss and accuracy at epoch t . Training stops if:

$$\forall k \in \{1, \dots, \text{patience}\}, \quad \mathcal{L}_{t-k} \geq \mathcal{L}_{t-k-1} - \delta \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{A}_{t-k} \leq \mathcal{A}_{t-k-1} + \delta$$

This dual-metric early stopping criterion improves robustness over single-metric strategies, particularly in settings where accuracy and loss are not perfectly aligned.

Algorithm 3 Early Stopping Procedure

Require: Validation loss \mathcal{L}_t , validation accuracy \mathcal{A}_t , patience p , improvement threshold δ , model M

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1: Initialize: best_loss  $\leftarrow \infty$ , best_acc  $\leftarrow 0$ , counter  $\leftarrow 0$ 
2: for each epoch  $t$  do
3:   Evaluate current  $\mathcal{L}_t, \mathcal{A}_t$ 
4:   improved  $\leftarrow$  False
5:   if  $\mathcal{L}_t < \text{best\_loss} - \delta$  then
6:     best_loss  $\leftarrow \mathcal{L}_t$ 
7:     improved  $\leftarrow$  True
8:   end if
9:   if monitor accuracy and  $\mathcal{A}_t > \text{best\_acc} + \delta$  then
10:    best_acc  $\leftarrow \mathcal{A}_t$ 
11:    improved  $\leftarrow$  True
12:   end if
13:   if improved then
14:     counter  $\leftarrow 0$ 
15:     Save model checkpoint  $M$ 
16:   else
17:     counter  $\leftarrow$  counter + 1
18:     if counter  $\geq p$  then
19:       Stop training
20:     end if
21:   end if
22: end for
```

S2 Additional Figures

Figure S2: F1 Score per class for the best trained model (EfficientNet-B5)